

MANUFACTURE OF CO-CURED INTEGRAL HAT-STIFFENED PANEL WITH AUTOMATED FIBRE PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Hat-stiffened composite panels have been widely used in the manufacture of spacecraft and aircraft. This experimental study investigates the feasibility of automated fiber placement used in the manufacture of composite skin of integral co-cured hat-stiffened panels. To achieve good manufacturing quality and simplify manufacturing process, a new form of flexible inner mold was design for the enclosed cavity between hat-shaped stringer and skin. Influences of flexible mold and layup process parameters on structure geometrics accuracies and fiber distribution were evaluated in both FEA and experimental methods. Results shows that when inner mold's elastic modulus is closed to that of flexible compact roller, the influence of mold's elastic modulus on microscopic fiber distribution of skin can be ignored. Moreover, in this condition, a good curing quality can be achieved, which means the thickness deviation of hat-stiffened composites panel could be smaller than 8%. Actual results are in good accordance with FEA analysis. By the optimization of process factors proposed in this paper, automated and integrated manufacture of hat-stiffened composite panel can be achieved, with improved surface quality and geometrics accuracies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hat-shaped stiffened composite has been become one of the most common structure forms in aircraft fuselage, due to its outstanding stability and structural efficiency [1]. It consists of composite skin and several hat-shaped stringers. Currently, hat-shaped stiffened composite structure is mainly manufactured by co-bonded process, in which hat-shaped stringers are cured in advance and then the cured stringer and uncured skin are co-cured in autoclave [2-3]. In this way, good geometry accuracy of composite structure can be achieved, while the cost could be very high because it needs two curing cycle. Thus, to decrease the manufacturing cost of stiffened composites, co-curing process is proposed. Compared with co-bonded method, uncured stringers and skin would be cured simultaneously in co-cured method which means that the cost can be reduced significantly. Moreover, related studies showed that co-cured method can obtain a better interface strength between stringers and skin [4], greater deformations of the final part than with secondary bonding [5].

Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) process [6-7] is one of the most advanced manufacturing processes for composite. During this process, several prepreg tows can be laid on the mandrel surface under the compaction of a flexible roller. Because each prepreg tow can be cut, clamped and restarted respectively, AFP is perfect process for the manufacturing of fuselage skin, wing, air-inlet and some other high-quality, high volume contoured structures.

The main purpose of this paper is to conduct a preliminary study on the manufacture quality of hat-stiffened panels which the skin is manufactured by AFP and co-cured with hat-shaped stringers. Then it can provide reference to the integral manufacture of aircraft fuselage.

2 DESIGN OF INNER MOLD FOR CO-CURED INTEGRAL HAT-STIFFENED COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED VIA AFP

The typical cross section of hat-stiffened panel with on hat-stringer is shown as Fig.1. In this paper, the hat-stringer is laid up by hand on the surface of cavity block due to its complex shape and the limited deformation of flexible roller. Then the skin is laid up by AFP and co-cured with stringer in autoclave. At last, when the mold was removed, integral hat-stiffened panels can be obtained.

Figure 1: Cross section of hat-stiffened composite plate

However, there is a cavity between skin and hat stringer which should be filled by an appropriate inner mold to avoid the generation of some defects during the manufacturing process (shown in Fig 2.).

Figure 2: Typical defects induced by improper filled mold for cavity: (a) excessive out-of-plate deformation of prepreg during AFP; (b) uneven thickness and (c) non-common resin flow causing by non-uniform cured pressure.

2.1 Requirements of inner mold

Thus, one of the key points to the manufacture of integral hat-stiffened panel via co-curing and AFP is to design a proper inner mold for the cavity. To achieve high manufacturing quality, the requirements of cavity filling mold can be listed as blow:

- (1) The mold should have perfect anti-deformability, to decrease its compressive deformation and prepreg plies' out of -plate deformation under the action of compact force, during the layup of skin by AFP.
- (2) The mold can provide enough and uniform curing pressure during the co-curing process. Moreover, the inner surface quality of stringer and skin also should be considered.
- (3) The mold can be removed as easy as possible.

2.2 Design of inner mold

To meet above requirements and overcome the shortage of current mold [8], a new form of flexible mold is proposed in this paper, which is composed by silicone bladder, silicone filler and vacuum film bladder (shown in Fig.3). During AFP process, the cavity is filled by silicone bladder along with silicone filler, to obtain enough support for the prepreg under the action of compact roller. While the silicon filler will be replaced by vacuum film bladder, which can compose vacuum sealing system along with the upper vacuum film and other part of mold, in the co-curing process of hat-shaped stringer and skin. In this way, the curing pressure for stringer and the skin on it is uniform and same with the pressure in autoclave. Moreover, flexible silicone bladder can be used to avoid the adverse effect of vacuum film's wrinkle on composite panel surface quality and can be taken out from the enclosed cavity with vacuum.

Figure 3: Mold of enclosed cavity for integral hat-stiffened composites structure manufactured by AFP and co-curing process, (a) the mold for AFP process and (b) the mold for co-curing process.

3 OPTIMISATION OF INTEGRAL CO-CURED HAT-STIFFENED PANELS WITH AFP

As shown in Fig 4, when a prepreg tow are laid on the flexible mold with compaction force, out-of-plane fibre waviness will be induced by the compressive deformation of flexible mold, which will decrease the mechanical performance of composite part significantly [9-10].

Figure 4: Deformation of prepreg on the top of flexible mold with compact force.

Besides out-of-plane fibre waviness, nonuniform thickness will be also resulted from uneven curing pressure due to improper designation of silicone bladder. Thus, to eliminate out-of-plane fibre waviness and improve dimensional accuracies, it is important to study the compressive and thermal deformation of silicon bladder and filler.

3.1 Compressive deformation of inner mold during AFP

To understand the scale of out-of-plane fibre waviness induced by compressive deformation of flexible inner mold, a FEA model was established to study the relationship between compressive deformation of flexible inner mold with different material and processing parameters, which can be seen in Fig 5.

Figure 5: FEA model to study the compressive deformation of flexible mold during AFP

Obviously, key influence factors of inner mold's compressive deformation are the elastic modulus of silicon rubber and the compaction force of AFP. Simulation results can be seen in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Inner mold's compression with different elastic modulus

Results show that compression of flexible mold decrease with increasing elastic modulus of silicon rubber, in the common level of compaction force. When inner mold's elastic modulus is larger than that of flexible compact roller, the influence of inner mold on the compressive deformation can be ignored.

3.2 Thermal expansion of inner mold during curing process

During the curing process, the thermal expansion of inner mold will lead to an extra pressure on prepreg stacks, which can be a great influence on the thickness of final parts [11]. Thus, thermal expansion behaviour of flexible mold during curing process is also investigated in FEA method. The influence of silicon bladder's shape and its elastic modulus are involved in this paper. Results show that the lower elastic modulus is, the larger thermal stress of silicon bladder is, leading to desirable transfer of curing pressure and uniform thickness of composite structure.

Figure 7: Thermal expansion of inner mold with different elastic modulus

In a common level of compaction force of AFP (which is about 500N), the greatest influence factor is the elastic modulus of inner flexible mold. If silicon rubber elastic modulus is too low, a uniform thickness of final parts will be obtained, but an obvious out-of-plane fibre waviness in the skin will be induced by lack of support. While if silicon rubber elastic modulus is too large, out-of-plane fibre waviness will be reduced but curing pressure of prepreg stack became to be non-uniform.

According to the above analysis, the elastic modulus of inner mold should be close to that of compaction flexible roller of AFP to achieve a high quality of hat-stiffened panel. Generally, the elastic modulus of compaction roller is 5 MPa which can provide a good deformation and fit for complex structures.

4 EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

An integral hat-stiffened composite panel is manufactured in method as indicated in this paper, which can be seen in Fig 8.

Figure 8: Manufacturing process of integral hat-stiffened double curved panel with AFP

To verify above theoretical analysis results, elastic moduli of silicon rubber used for flexible mold are 2.47MPa, 5.54MPa, 9.39MPa, 11.2MPa and 14.3MPa, respectively.

What can be seen from Fig.9 is that when the silicon bladder's modulus is 5.54MPa, the quality of cured composite is the best. Silicon bladder with too big elastic modulus will make a degradation of curing quality. Possible reasons for this phenomenon are explained as below. With same coefficient of thermal expansion, the thermal expansion of silicon bladder around its corner will be larger than other area due to its thickness difference. The difference of pressure induced by thermal expansion of silicon bladder would be more significant with growing elastic modulus of silicon bladder. Then fibre

waviness, imperfect geometrical shape around the corner, even local macroscopic out-of-plane deformation of composite skin would be resulted from an oversized elastic modulus of silicon bladder. As a result, the silicon bladder's elastic modulus should be around 5MPa for the manufacturing of hat-stiffened composite involved in this paper, to improve both layup quality and curing quality.

Figure 9: Influence of inner mold's elastic modulus on hat-stiffened panel's fibre distribution

The same conclusion can be made for the influence of silicon bladder's modulus on co-cured composite panel according to Fig. 10. Silicon bladder, which elastic modulus is 5MPa, can provide a much more uniform curing pressure than other silicon bladder and achieve a high geometric accuracy of co-cured hat-stiffened panels, which thickness deviation is smaller than 7%. In conclusion, actual results are in good accordance with FEA analysis.

(a) Measurement point (b) Influence of inner mold's elastic modulus on thickness

Figure 10: Actual thickness distribution of integral hat-stiffened panel

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a new integrated and automated manufacturing process for hat-stiffened composites was proposed. In this process, the composite skin is manufactured by AFP and then co-cured with uncured hat-shaped stringers. Based on geometric features of hat-stiffened composites part and characteristic of different procedure in manufacturing process, a new flexible assemble mold was designed.

To achieve good quality of final parts, the compressive and thermal deformation of flexible inner mold were simulated in FEA method. Increasing elastic modulus of inner mold can be attribute to good fibre distribution but poor uniformity of thickness in final parts. What can be found is when the elastic modulus of inner mold is close to that of compaction flexible roller of AFP, a high quality of hat-stiffened panel can be obtained. Experimental results are in good accordance with FEA analysis.

The process proposed in this paper is highly feasible to manufacture double curved hat-stiffened composite structures in co-curing process combining with AFP. Geometric accuracy can be guaranteed

by the optimization of mold's properties and processing parameters. The mechanical performance of as-manufactured hat-stiffened composites will be further studied in the future.

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